

Basic Technology Associated with Orientation and mobility Training

K.Umamaheswari , Assistant Professor, Department of Special Education and Hearing Impairment, Kalasalingam Academy of Research and Education, Krishnankoil, Virudhunagar District, Tamilnadu.

Abstract:

This article provide an overview of basic technology of Orientation and mobility Training used in Training that teaches the visually impaired to move freely and independently in the environment is called orientation and movement training. This is one of the most important educational subjects for the visually impaired, which requires serious effort, continuous training of family teachers and personal practice. When in familiar surroundings, people with visual impairments may prefer to travel without a cane or a sighted guide. They may employ a variety of strategies to keep themselves from running into things and perhaps getting wounded. These methods are limited to applications with which the user is already familiar. In training, they use several techniques to protect themselves from hitting objects and possibly hurting themselves. These techniques are used only in areas that are already familiar.

Introduction:

People with vision impairments can learn how to navigate their surroundings with the aid of orientation and mobility training. It educates kids to be aware of their location and to make plans in order to reach their goals. A person with vision impairment navigates their world differently. Even simple routes can be difficult or dangerous, needing caution and preparation to complete successfully. A person with vision impairment who receives orientation and mobility (O&M) training learns how to properly navigate their surroundings and use mobility aids like a guide dog or white cane. When visually impaired persons are in familiar places, they may want to travel without a cane or a sighted guide. They may use several techniques to navigate.

Orientation and mobility Training

Orientation has traditionally been defined as the process of using one's senses to establish one's position and relationship to other objects in the environment. People with visual impairment can benefit from orientation and mobility training to better understand where they are in space and where they want to go. Orientation and mobility services are among the associated services provided to eligible children as part of their individual education plans (IEP), with the focus defined by an orientation and mobility specialist's examination of the child. Because children have a variety of visual abilities, orientation and mobility education can cover a wide range of topics.

Sight- Guided Technique:

The most popular and effective method for assisting a person with vision impairment in moving around is the sight-guided technique. By using this technique, a sighted companion walks behind the person who is visually impaired, providing guidance on path and direction as well as tailored instructions. Both the sighted and the visually impaired receive training. A skilled guide helps the blind person navigate a variety of situations, including climbing and descending stairs, navigating tight spaces and entrances, and avoiding or navigating over obstacles.

In actuality, not only can the youngster learn to properly use the sight-guided technique, but the parent and other family members can as well. With some experience, the guide and the individual with the visual impairment are able to communicate. The guide is then spared from having to deliver instructions verbally each time. The visually impaired person becomes aware of changes in direction, obstructions in the path, and other information via the guide's hand pressure, walking tempo, and other physical cues.

Walking Alone Techniques

It is crucial for a visually impaired individual to be able to walk by themselves. With this ability, he may be more independent, boost his confidence, and be a master of his own will. It is especially helpful for carrying out personal grooming and daily life tasks. A person who has received the necessary training in walking alone can defend himself against bumping into things and injuring himself. The following describes the different strategies you can educate the visually impaired to help them walk safely on their own.

Hand Trailing Technique

Train the disabled person learns to follow walls, table edges, and other such things with the back of his hand. The individual to be followed should stand close to the object and extend the arm closest to it, making sure the backs of his fingers make contact with the object. Next, he should be practiced walking by using his fingers to trace the surface of objects (such as the wall or the table) to reach his objective. Because the insides of the fingers are fragile and can get injured while trailing a rough object, you must make sure that only the backs of the fingers touch the object to be trailed.

Additionally, the hand and arm shouldn't be too close to the body when trailing since if they are, the person may not be able to stop quickly in case his hand comes into contact with something. Instead, when following, the person's arm should be stretched away from the body so that his hand detects an obstruction before he does.

Protective Techniques

For blind people protection when moving around your home, you must know how to use the higher and lower protective techniques. These methods stop accidents involving open drawers, doors, tables, chairs, and other potential objects from injuring the head, face, and torso. Remember when you are learning these skills that the only ways to protect your feet, calves, and knees are to use a walker or a long cane held diagonally in front of you.

Upper Body Protective Technique

The first step in learning the upper protection method is to place one arm shoulder to elbow parallel to the ground. After that, bend your arm at the elbow so that your hand is about 10 inches in front of your face and your forearm crosses your body diagonally. Bending forward from this posture enables your forearm to act as a cushion in case you contact with anything. This position can be adjusted, or the wearer can cover their face with a helmet or visor if arthritis or a lack of strength prevents them from sustaining it. Your hand with the

palm facing outward towards your face. To shield your fingers, point them slightly in the direction of your face.

Lower Protective Technique

To protect the torso using the lower protective technique, start by reaching the arm straight out in front at about a 45-degree angle, like reaching to shake hands with someone. This will protect your upper body. Swing the arm out to the side, about a foot away from your body, while keeping it extended. Curl your fingers slightly inward and face your palm towards the body, slightly below the waist. When you come into touch with chairs, tables, and other thigh-high objects, the back of your forearm and hand will shield your central body. Objects like a paper towel tube, rolled-up magazine, or ruler can be utilised to offer total covering if a person is unable to extend their arm to

shield their body while utilising any of these ways.

Squaring off

The squaring off approach is used when there's an open region that needs to be crossed. They will turn around without changing their course when they encounter an area devoid of impediments. They will have their backs and heels up against the wall. To ensure that the area is clear, we encourage children to look and listen while maintaining their "nose and toes pointed where they want to go." They have two options: they can make continuous touch or use a diagonal cane to cover their upper body with one hand while maintaining a straight course until they reach the opposite side.

Conclusion:

As a recently blind person or a person with visual impairment, it makes sense that you would be worried about travelling securely and avoiding mishaps. Orientation and mobility, or O&M for short, is specialised training that assists individuals with visual impairments in relearning or acquiring the skills necessary for safe, independent travel within their homes and communities. Several orientation tactics that might help maintain safety in the home and other surroundings were examined in this lecture. These consist of trailing, room familiarisation, finding dropped objects, and the protective strategy. It is crucial to emphasise once more that in situations when functional eyesight is inadequate, a long white cane or dog guide is a necessary mobility aid for maintaining freedom and safety in strange places.

Reference:

- 1) <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/orientation-and-mobility>
- 2) <https://www.pathstoliteracy.org/overview-orientation-and-mobility/>
- 3) <https://ies.ed.gov/ncser/pubs/20083007/orientation.asp>
- 4) Pierangelo, R., and Giuliani, G.A. (2004). *Transition Services in Special Education*. Boston: Pearson Education.
- 5) Allison, C., and Sanspree, M.J. (2006). Persons With Visual Impairments. In R. Gargiulo (Ed.), *Special Education in Contemporary Society* (2nd ed., pp. 480–519). Belmont, CA: Thomson Learning Corporation.
- 6) <https://ies.ed.gov/ncser/pubs/20083007/orientation.asp>
- 7) Hill, E.W. (1986). Orientation and Mobility. In G.T. Scholl (Ed.), *Foundations of Education for Blind and Visually Handicapped Children and Youth: Theory and Practice* (pp. 315–340). New York: AFB Press.
- 8) <https://www.oib-tac.org/sites/www.oib-tac.org/files/2023-03/Lesson%205-%20Orientation%20and%20Safety%20in%20the%20Home%202021.1.25.pdf>
- 9) <http://parentmobility.com/index.php/squaring-off-technique/>